

Role of Annie Besant in the Indian National Congress (The First Woman President)

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Abstract

Annie Besant was an Irish lady who came to India in 1893 as a Theosophist and made it her permanent home. She occupies an honoured place in the annals of Hindu Revivalism. She was a great advocate of national education and swadeshi. She entered the political field in 1914 and founded Home Rule League in 1916. She demanded Home Rule for India. Her popularity as National Leader can be gauged from the fact that the Congress elected her to preside over its Calcutta session in 1917. So Mrs. Besant became the first women president of the Indian National Congress to preside over the 32nd session which was held at Calcutta in the year 1917. Her presidential address was an elaborate thesis of India's self-government. She outlined the programme for India's future. That India should move towards her ancient institutions like the village panchayat, etc. Mrs. Besant strongly pleaded for liberty and freedom. She believed that the establishment of self government was imperative in India. It is necessary to the self-respect and dignity of the people. The demand for self rule means the need for freedom of nation.

Keywords: Self Government, Home Rule, Hindu Revivalism, National Education and Swadeshi.

Introduction

‘To see India free, to see her hold up her head among the Nations, to see her sons and daughters respected everywhere, to see her worthy of her mighty past, engaged in building a yet mightier future, is not this working for, worth living for and worth dying for?’ - Annie Besant in her Presidential address at Calcutta Session in 1917.

Annie Besant, one of the important leaders of the Theosophical Movement, began the Home Rule movement in 1916. She founded the organization ‘All India Home Rule League’, and it was through this organization that Annie Besant had popularized the movement. This organization had established various branches spread all over the country. Even it had a branch in England through which public opinion was sought to be moulded in favour of the Home Rule for the Indians.

Rise of Nationalism in India

Nationalism is a great unifying force. It is a sort of spiritual bond which brings together persons having unity of language, religion, race, literature, history and customs. It is further strengthened by

common economic and political interests and also geographical unity. Nationalism means the feeling of oneness and unity among the people of a nation or patriotic feeling, principles and policy of national independence is termed as nationalism.

Rapid Growth of Nationalism

Indian nationalism is a modern phenomenon. It came into being during the British period as a result of the action and inter-action of numerous subjective and objective and factors which developed within the society under the conditions of British rule and impact of world forces. National awakening was the historical development during the second half of the 19th and the first half of the 20th century. Political awakening in India was a natural reaction against the aggressive British imperialism and oppressive British rule. The alien rule and its bureaucrats, their indifferent attitude, their policies and programs were vital factors which aroused nationalism in India.

The significant role in the growth of national awakening was the spread of western education. The Indians who had received English education studied the political systems of the western nations and were moved by the aspirations for self-government and for representative institutions. This process was greatly accelerated by Lord William Bentinck's decision, taken in accordance with the famous Educational Minute of Lord Macaulay, to adopt English as the medium of instruction for imparting Western education. Whatever might have been the motives of Macaulay in introducing Western education, the inevitable result was that the young intellectuals of India began to press for freedom.

The role of press helped to mould Indian nationalism. Some English newspapers were owned by the English and some owned by the Indian. Newspapers both in English and Indian languages increased in number after the third quarter of the 19th century. It had its genesis in the political organizations that came to light prior to the establishment of sentiments of the natives of different parts of the Indian subcontinent and consequently it paved the way for the firm rooting of the Indian nationalism in British India.

Under the existing law, an European could be tried only by an European Judge. In order to do away with the racial discrimination, Mr. Rippon, the Law Member of the Executive Council, moved a Bill in 1883. Indians welcomed the move, but the Europeans demanded the withdrawal of Ilbert Bill. This awakened the Indians to the need for an effective national organization to champion the cause of the people and represent their grievances to Government.

Birth of Indian National Congress

The National Movement of India assumed an institutionalised form in the Indian National Congress set up in 1885. It was organised by Allan Octavian Hume, a retired Indian Civil Servant under the direction from Lord Dufferin, then the Governor General of India. The main purpose of this organisation was to provide a 'safety- valve' for mental, moral social and political regeneration of the people of India. Prof. Sundar Ram, who was one of the seventy two participants in the first session men representing different parts of India met in the Hall of the Gokuldas Rajpal Sanskrit College, Bombay on December 25, 1885 and founded the Indian National Congress.

Mrs. Annie Besant as the President of Congress

Mr. Besant became the first woman to be conferred the highest honour in the History of the congress. Mrs. Besant was elected to preside over the 32nd session of the Indian National Congress at Calcutta in December 1917. Since the foundation of Indian Nation Congress in 1885, the largest numbers of delegates were represented at Calcutta session. The number of delegates of this Calcutta session was 4,967 which showed a remarkable leap in public spirit and patriotism of the people.

Mrs. Besant's address as president to the annual meeting of the congress was an important one. She declared that 'When I was humiliated by the British in India, you believed in my integrity and good faith; while I was crushed under the heel of bureaucratic power, you acclaimed me as your leader, while I was silenced and unable to defend myself, you defended me and won for me release from internment. I was proud to serve in lowliest fashion, but you lifted me up and placed me before the world as your chosen representative. I..... lay on the Altar of the Mother, and together we shall cry, more by service than by words Vande mataram''.

The two hour speech contained many things such as a historical account of Indians. Her presidential address was an elaborate thesis of India's self-government. She outlined the programme for India's future. That India should move towards her ancient institutions like the village council, the village panchayat.etc.

Mrs. Besant strongly pleaded for liberty and freedom. She believed that the establishment of self-government was imperative in India. It is necessary to the self-respect and dignity of the people. She further added that; 'The condition of India's usefulness to the Empire is India's freedom'. Mrs. Besant voiced protest against British powers. She opined that the British government has taken less interest to factors like child education, difficulties in sanitation and medical relief and agricultural development.

The congress thus became a big platform of two wings and marks the beginnings of a new phase in the battle for the freedom. The main resolution was that dealing with the question of self government. Some of the resolutions were following: a) The congress strongly opined that the education of boys and girls to be under Indian control as well as essentially in Indian spirit. b) The Congress called upon the people of India to work for the success of the Swadeshi Movement, by making earnest and sustained efforts to promote the growth of indigenous industries and to give preference to Indian products over imported commodities. c) The congress expressed satisfaction to His Majesty's Secretary of state of India on behalf of the imperial government of establishing responsible government of India. d) Congress resolved and regretted that the British Indians of South Africa and East Africa still face disabilities, which materially affected unjustly and unduly restricted their movements in those parts of Europe. It said that the local authorities should take the responsibilities to remove disabilities in those places e) The Congress recognized that the principles of social justice and right for the depressed classes.

Impact of Calcutta Session

The Calcutta session of the Indian National Congress became memorable. Mrs. Besant introduced the tradition that the president of the annual session of the congress would head the organization throughout the following year till the next session. The activity of the congress earlier was largely an annual two or three-day gathering and speech-making session. The activity filled the organization round the year aimed to force the British concede India's demand for self-rule. By her efforts, the congress session brought nearer the congress and the Home Rule League. Apart from this, the Home Rule League had already adopted and populated the tricolored flag in Red, white and Green the colours chosen to adorn the flag horizontally in equal proportions. The design continued to be the congress flag till 1930. In 1931, the saffron colour replaced the red, and a charka was inscribed on the white band in the middle of the flag. It was this flag which with a few other modifications ultimately became the flag of free India.

Conclusion

Her contribution to the cause of India's freedom was immense. Besant's political aim was to see India as a free nation which would add its due share to the progress of the world in the future. One of the biggest personalities Md. Ali Jinnah said that: 'No other person has worked and served the cause of India with that singleness of purpose, devotion and transparent sincerity' as has Mrs. Besant. She has sacrificed all that she could, what for? -Only for the freedom of India. Mrs. Besant is, thus a strange combination of pragmatism political wisdom and zealous enthusiasm in promoting a truly Indian spirit.

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